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Perception of teaching fraternity regarding library 2.0 services for teaching, learning and research in academic libraries of Gujarat state

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Abstract: This study looked into how the academic library in Gujarat State used web 2.0 tools to deliver library services for research, learning, and teaching. A questionnaire was used as a data gathering tool by the researchers, who used a descriptive survey method. 584 faculty members from various universities and colleges in the state of Gujarat made up the study's population. To determine the responses to the research questions, frequency counts, percentages, and means were used to evaluate the data taken from the copies of questionnaires retrieved from respondents. The findings indicated that the most popular Web 2.0 applications are instant messaging and social networking sites. The main purpose to use web 2.0 tools for teaching fraternity is academic and to connect with friends and family members. Lack of connectivity and skills are major obstacles for using library 2.0 services.

Keywords: Web 2.0, Library services, Library 2.0, Gujarat State

Introduction

The emergence of web-based communities, server-client based services, and applications including blogs, RSS, Wikis, social networking sites, and file-sharing websites has been facilitated by Web 2.0 ideals. Web 2.0 is a collection of internet usage trends and tools, according to a number of academics. In Darcy DiNucci's "Fragmented Future," a book on the future of computers, the phrase "Web 2.0" first surfaced. Web 2.0 was still in its infancy compared to its current widespread use at that time. Tim O'Reilly and Dale Dougherty first proposed and popularized Web 2.0 at the O'Reilly Media 2004 conference to define the trends and business models that had weathered the 1990s technology sector market meltdown. Web 2.0 tools make it possible for academics, staff, students, and the general public to exchange and grow their knowledge, culture, and information. Various literature review and expert of the field of computer science stated that that the Web 2.0 revolution is a social one. Due to their focus on community building and social features, Web 2.0 applications see higher usage rates than Web 1.0 static websites and applications.

The basic goals of academic libraries are to gather, organize, and make accessible published information as well as to spread knowledge. Library resources like books, journals, and monographs are being created in electronic formats in the modern period. Academic libraries are undergoing a significant paradigm shift in how they support users and provide services in response to these difficulties. It has been suggested that the features of Web 2.0 enable users to engage the library in two-way communication and knowledge exchanges. Web 2.0 has the potential to foster participatory networking where librarians and users can communicate, cooperate, and generate material. Logs, wikis, social networking sites, social tagging, instant messaging, RSS, file sharing websites, social bookmarking, and online virtual games are examples of Web 2.0 applications. There is potential for many libraries using Web 2.0 applications to market their offerings. This implementation of Web 2.0 tools in services of conventional library is widely known as Library 2.0. Steven Bon in 2009 describes Library 2.0 as "Academic libraries always had elements of the Web 2.0 to them, but without the 2.0 technology. Much the same, the exchange of information in real-time (think phone and F2F reference) is not new to libraries, but we now have the convenience,

immediacy and community presence of the real-time web world. While Wikipedia describes Library 2.0 services as User-generated/user participation library service evolution which Enable more user participation and reach out to users in the spaces they prefer to be. The main characteristic of library 2.0 is more user - engaged instruction sessions in shot we can say that in heart of Library 2.0 “The user is participant, co - creator, builder and consultant whether the product is virtual or physical”

Blogs, wikis, streaming video, content aggregators, instant messaging, and social networks are all combined to form Library 2.0, a sort of hybrid technology. Library 2.0 records users with tags, IM chats with librarians, and wiki entries with other users. It also remembers people when they log in and lets them change OPAC data and metadata (and catalogues all of these for others to use). The user can choose to make all or a portion of their profile public, and they can check to see if other users have checked out, borrowed, or lent similar products. The traditional catalogue is combined with a massive user-driven catalogue.

The library community has been investigating the potential of Web 2.0 to keep improving library services ever since, but Library 2.0, which was adopted by libraries in the beginning as a web revolution, was static because online public access catalogues (OPACs) require users to search for the information, while some users may be new to incorporating Web 2.0 techniques by gathering data relating to a user (checked-out items, preferred searches and search alerts). As a result, they wouldn't offer suggestions like Amazon.com, a Web 2.0 service that is more dynamic. Several systems allow users to tag phrases that they have defined and that may signify different things to different people. Subject headings may give librarians, especially catalogers using regulated vocabulary systems like the Library of Congress, the idea to allow users to contribute their own terms, which could subsequently result in anarchy.

Objective of Study

The objectives of this research is to investigate how the teaching community perceive library 2.0 services provided by academic libraries in Gujarat State using Web 2.0 platforms for effective teaching, learning, and research. In particular, the study aims to

- To assess the extent to which web 2.0 is being used
- To investigate the reasons for the use of web 2.0
- To determine the barriers that prevent the effective use of web 2.0

Methodology of Study

This study used a descriptive approach to investigate into the utilization of Web 2.0 tools for providing library services for research, teaching, and learning. This is due to the fact that descriptive design allows for very compact and enormous population. Researcher has decided to collect the information through the primary and secondary data for the present study.

The secondary data was obtained from peer-reviewed journals, magazines, research reports, full-text conference proceedings, peer-reviewed work on the topic of web 2.0 and library 2.0 that has been published and unpublished, blogs run by experts, websites of different academic libraries, search engines, and various subject databases, as well as a consortium of eBooks and e-journals.

The teacher fraternity in Gujarat state served as samples for the researcher as she employed structured questionnaires to gather primary data for the study. MS Excel and SPSS have been used to examine the data statistically.

The population for the study comprises of all the teaching staff in various colleges and universities in Gujarat State. There was five hundred eighty four teaching staff from target population has given their views regarding Library 2.0 or Library services given with help of web 2.0 tools. The sample was selected through simple random sample techniques for the ease of data collection.

This study employed the questionnaire as instrument for data collection. The questionnaire was constructed by the researchers. Questionnaire was administered through both online Google form and offline (Printed) format. In present study following variables were used from data collected.

Below tabular data presents the demographic appearances of the respondents.

Variables	Incorporating a range.	Scale of Measurement used
Age group	Below 30	Five point interval Scale
	30 - 40	
	40 - 50	
	50 – 60	
	61 & Above	
Gender	Male	Two point Interval Scale
	Female	
Designation	Assist. Professor	Three point Interval Scale
	Associate Professor	
	Assistant Professor	
Dependent variable	frequency of using Web 2.0 tools	Five point Likert Scale
Independent Variable	Purpose of using Web 2.0 tools	Three point Likert Scale
Independent Variable	Problems in using various Library 2.0 services	Five point Likert Scale

Table 1 demographic information of Respondents

Description	Criteria	Frequency	Percent
Age	Below 30	238	40.8
	30 - 40	191	32.7
	40 - 50	97	16.6
	50 - 60	52	8.9
	61 & Above	6	1
Gender	Male	306	52.4
	Female	278	47.6
Designation	Assist. Professor	522	89.4
	Associate Professor	52	8.9
	HOD, Dean or principal of College	10	1.7
	Total	584	100

From Above table 1 we can reveals that out of 584 participants, majority of participants 40.8% are below 30 and 32.7% are between age group of 30 to 40. 16.6% are between age group of 40-50 and only 8.9% & 1 % are age group of 50-60 and 61 and above category respectively. If we see gender

as criteria, 52.4 % were male while 47.6 % were Female respondents in our survey. Respondents were further categorized on the bases of their designation in current job profile. By analyzing designation of respondents, we can say that majority 89.4 % respondents were Assistant professor, while 8.9% was on post of Associate Professor. Only 1.7 % respondents were on position of HOD, Dean or Principal of College.

Frequency analysis of collected data.

Web 2.0 tools used for library services	Never	Fortnightly	Weekly	Every alternate day	Daily
Wikis (Wikipedia)	47 - 8%	99 - 17%	130 - 22.3%	148 - 25.3%	160 - 27.4%
Instant Messaging (WhatsApp, F. Messenger, Hike)	15 - 2.6%	22 - 3.8%	59 - 10.1%	95 - 16.3%	393 - 67.3%
RSS feeds (Feedly etc.)	162 - 27.7%	105 - 18%	155 - 26.5%	115 - 19.7%	47 - 8%
Social Networking (FB, Instagram, Twitter)	49 - 8.4%	51 - 8.7%	105 - 18%	126 - 21.6%	253 - 43.3%
Podcasts (YouTube, Swayam)	47 - 8%	58 - 9.9%	120 - 20.5%	165 - 28.3%	194 - 33.2%
Tagging (Academia, Google Scholar, Research Gate, Orchid)	47 - 8%	82 - 14%	116 - 19.9%	162 - 27.7%	177 - 30.3%
Federated search (Discovery Search	84 - 14.4%	82 - 14%	174 - 29.8%	161 - 27.6%	83 - 14.2%
Personalized applications (Android Apps/ IOS apps)	68 - 11.6%	105 - 18%	123 - 21.1%	139 - 23.8%	149 - 25.5%
Blogs (Blogger, WordPress)	165 - 28.3%	125 - 21.4%	115 - 19.7%	102 - 17.5%	77 - 13.2%

From above table we can review that Majority of teachers are using Wikis as a tool for information source and using it on daily 27.4 %, or on alternate day 25.3% basis. Only 8% of respondents are not using Wikies. Instant Messaging services like WhatsApp, Facebook messenger or Hike are also most fevered Web 2.0 tools by teachers. 67.3% respondents are using it on daily basis and 16.3% are suing on alternate day basis. Only 2.6% have not used Instant Messaging for academic purpose. Though RSS fees are very strong Web 2.0 tools for academic purpose majority of respondents 27.7% never used it and 26.5 % used it only once a week. Only 8% are using on daily bases. Social Networking sites are most powerful tools for teaching fraternity as 43.3% are using on daily bases and 21.6 % are using on every alternate day while 8.4 % have revealed that they have never used it. Video podcast like YouTube and Swayam NPTEL videos are also most used web 2.0 tools for academic purpose. 33.2 % respondents are using on daily bases and 28.3 % are using on every alternate day. Tagging services like Academia, Google Scholar, Research Gate or orchid are also favorable as 30.3 % and 27.7 % are using on daily and alternate day bases respectively. Federated search or Discovery Search services and personalized library applications are equally used by teaching fraternity. Blogging is also considered as strong tool for information dissemination it is not much used by respondents as majority of responded (28.3%) that they never used blogging services.

Table 2 Purpose of using web 2.0 tools

Purpose of using web 2.0 tools	Disagree	Natural	Agree	Mean
Fun/Entertainment	110 - 19%	172 - 29%	302 - 52%	2.33
Publishing Acquiring Information	69 - 12%	129 - 22%	386 - 66%	2.54

(Postings On Fb, WhatsApp, Insta. Etc.)				
Academic Purposes	25 - 4%	74 - 13%	485 - 83%	2.79
Accessing Library Services	106 - 18%	142 - 24%	336 - 58%	2.39
Professional Collaborations	151 - 26%	125 - 21%	308 - 53%	2.27
Contact With Family Members, Friends, Etc.	60 - 10%	112 - 19%	412 - 71%	2.6
Add Tags To Internet Bookmarks, Research Papers, Pictures, Graphs	84 - 14%	130 - 22%	370 - 63%	2.49

Form above table 2 we can conclude that majority of respondents are agreeing with all-purpose define by researchers as all-purpose have mean score more than 2 on scale of 3. If we talk about individual criteria, Majority of respondents 52% (Mean - 2.33) are agreeing that they use web 2.0 tools as fun or entertainment Purpose. 66% (Mean - 2.54) of them are using it for the purpose of Publishing Acquiring Information like Postings on Fb, WhatsApp, Instagram Etc. 83 % (Mean - 2.79) have accepted that they are using for academic purpose. 58% (Mean - 2.39) are using for accessing library services and 53 % (Mean - 2.27) are using for professional collaboration. 71 % (Mean - 2.60) are using web 2.0 tools to connect with friends and family members. 63% (Mean - 2.49) are using to add Tags to Internet Bookmarks, Research Papers, Pictures, and Graphs etc.

Table 3 Obstacles in Using Library 2.0 services

Obstacles	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	Mean
Lack of awareness	28 - 5%	46 - 8%	127 - 22%	187 - 32%	196 - 34%	3.82
Lack of skill	33 - 6%	63 - 11%	117 - 20%	247 - 42%	124 - 21%	3.63
Lack of Connectivity	37 - 6%	65 - 11%	145 - 25%	213 - 36%	124 - 21%	3.55
Lack of technical knowledge	33 - 6%	91 - 16%	139 - 24%	193 - 33%	128 - 22%	3.5
Lack of technical support	34 - 6%	92 - 16%	140 - 24%	186 - 32%	132 - 23%	3.5
Privacy concerns	34 - 6%	72 - 12%	181 - 31%	175 - 30%	122 - 21%	3.48
Not Interested	64 - 11%	103 - 18%	176 - 30%	162 - 28%	79 - 14%	3.15
Reluctance to Change	44 - 8%	85 - 15%	170 - 29%	170 - 29%	115 - 20%	3.39

Respondents were asked to give their perceptions regarding obstacles that might be occur while using library 2.0 services. Majority of respondents (34 % strongly agree and 32 % agree) were agree that Lack of awareness is probable obstacle in using of web 2.0 tools. Respondents believed that Lack of skills (21 % and 42 % respectively for strongly agree and agree) is concern in usage of Library 2.0 services while lack of Connectivity, Lack of technical knowledge, Lack of technical support, Privacy concerns, Not Interested and Reluctance to Change is also a major obstacle for use of library 2.0 services.

Conclusion and further Discussion

The interactive nature of Web 2.0 has given libraries and information operations a new dimension. It has also provided services that library users of all categories should take advantage of in order to stay current on their fields and acquire knowledge effectively in the modern age. Teachers have to be always updated to preach students and make them competent. In this competitive paradigm shift

they can take help of various services that is being provided with help of web 2.0 tools by academic libraries. We can conclude that among the numerous Web 2.0 tools, social networking sites and instant messaging are the mostly used ones tools by teaching fraternity. Teaching fraternity use web 2.0 tools for the academic purpose, followed by connect with friends and family members and publishing or acquiring information. The deployment of Web 2.0 tools by teaching fraternity to use services provided is complicated by the Lack of awareness, Lack of skills and Lack of connectivity of internet in library. This obstacles can be removed by effective user's orientation and one to one user guidance. On the other hand administration of educational institutions also provide necessary infrastructure to library staff so that they can implement various new services based on web 2.0 tools.

References:

- Abram, S. (2005). Web 2.0, library 2.0, and Librarian 2.0: Preparing for the 2.0 world. *SirsiDynix OneSource*, 2(1). Retrieved from http://www.imakenews.com/sirsi/e_article000505688.cfm
- Aharony, N. (2009). Librarians and information scientists in the blogosphere: An exploratory analysis. *Library & Information Science Research*, 13, 174-181.
- Anunobi, C.V. & Ogbonna, A. U (2012). Web 2.0 Use by Librarians in a State in Nigeria. *Developing Country Studies*, 2 (5), 57-66.
- Ashcroft, I. & Watts, C. (2005). ICT skills for information professionals in developing countries: Perspective from a study of the electronic environment in Nigeria: *IFLA Journal*, 31 (1), 6 – 12.
- Boateng, R., Mbarika, V., & Thomas, C. (2010). When Web 2.0 becomes an organizational learning tool: Evaluating Web 2.0 tools. *Development and Learning in Organizations*, 24(3), 17-20.
- Casey, M. E. & Savastinuk, L. C. (2006). Library 2.0 service for the next-generation library. *Library journal*, 131(14), 40-42.
- Chua, A. Y. K. & Goh, D. H. (2010). A study of Web 2.0 applications in library websites. *Library & Information Science Research*, 32(3), 203-211.
- Darries: Web 2.0 and Libraries 2.0: an introduction - Google Scholar. (n.d.). Retrieved December 30, 2020, from https://scholar.google.co.in/scholar?hl=en&as_sdt=0%2C5&q=http%3A%2F%2Fprints.rclis.org%2F14645%2F%2Fweb_2_and_library2_an_introduction.pdf&btnG=
- DiNucci, D. (1990). Fragmented future. *Print*, 53(4), 221-222.
- Harrison, A., Burrell, R., Velasquez, S., & Schreiner, L. (2017). Social Media Use in Academic Libraries: A Phenomenological Study. *Journal of Academic Librarianship*, 43(3), 248–256. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.acalib.2017.02.014>
- Linh, N. C. (2008). A survey of the application of Web 2.0 in Australasian university libraries. *Library Hi Tech*, 26(4), 630-653.
- Oni, O., Odaro-Ekhaguebo, K., & Akpoduado, E. (2018). Assessment of information communication technology proficiency of secondary school teachers. *Journal of Pedagogical Research*, 2(1), 46-54.
- O'Reilly, T. (2005). What is Web 2.0. Retrieved from <http://oreilly.com/web2/archive/what-is-web-20.html>
- Trivedi, D. M. (2016). Adoption of Social Networking Tools in Public University Libraries in Ghana. *International Journal of Innovative Research & Development*. Retrieved from https://www.academia.edu/24935755/Adoption_of_Social_Networking_Tools_in_Public_University_Libraries_in_Ghana